

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CONSUMER RIGHTS IN TÜRKİYE

NIJAT PANAHOV

Turiba University, PHD student
Riga, Latvia

Abstract. Consumer protection has evolved into a fundamental component of modern legal systems due to increasingly complex economic relations and the imbalance between producers and consumers. This study examines the historical and legal development of consumer protection in Türkiye, from Ottoman regulatory traditions to the contemporary framework shaped by European Union harmonization. The paper highlights the constitutional basis of consumer rights under Article 172 of the 1982 Constitution and analyzes the significance of Law No. 4077 (1995) and its replacement by Law No. 6502 (2013). It also evaluates recent developments concerning distance contracts, e-commerce, mediation, and consumer arbitration committees. The findings demonstrate that Turkish consumer law has transformed from a morality-based system into a comprehensive legal protection regime influenced by both domestic reforms and EU integration.

Keywords: Consumer Protection; Consumer Rights; Türkiye; EU Harmonization; Distance Contracts; E-Commerce; Consumer Arbitration Committees.

ИСТОРИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ ПРАВ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЕЙ В ТУРЦИИ

НИДЖАТ ПАНАХОВ

Докторант, Университет Туриба
Рига, Латвия

Аннотация. Защита прав потребителей превратилась в один из фундаментальных элементов современных правовых систем вследствие усложнения экономических отношений и дисбаланса между производителями и потребителями. В данном исследовании рассматривается историческое и правовое развитие защиты прав потребителей в Турции — от османских регулятивных традиций до современной системы, сформированной под влиянием гармонизации с правом Европейского Союза. В статье анализируются конституционные основы прав потребителей, закреплённые в статье 172 Конституции 1982 года, а также значение Закона № 4077 (1995 г.) и его замены Законом № 6502 (2013 г.). Кроме того, исследуются современные изменения, касающиеся дистанционных договоров, электронной коммерции, медиации и потребительских арбитражных комитетов. Результаты исследования показывают, что турецкое законодательство о защите прав потребителей трансформировалось из системы, основанной на моральных принципах, в комплексный правовой механизм защиты, сформированный как внутренними реформами, так и интеграцией с Европейским Союзом.

Ключевые слова: защита прав потребителей; права потребителей; Турция; гармонизация с ЕС; дистанционные договоры; электронная коммерция; потребительские арбитражные комитеты.

Introduction

The protection of consumers has taken on an important role within the current legal order because of the complexity of economic transactions and the unequal position of consumers vis-a-vis producers [12]. In today's economies, which are based on large-scale manufacturing and advanced technologies and which involve international trade, consumers are subjected to asymmetrical information flows, intense marketing efforts, and standardization, all of which reduce their negotiating abilities [6]. Thus, there is a need for effective legal rules for the protection of consumer rights.

Despite the common notion that consumer protection is a relatively new field in law, it dates back to the very beginning of law itself, as well as moral philosophies. There is historical proof that problems like fair measures, the quality of goods, and fraud were already being considered in the laws of ancient cultures. Nevertheless, the idea only gained popularity in the 19th century when the industrial revolution changed the dynamics of production and consumption. The shift from artisanal manufacturing to industrial manufacturing led to an unequal relationship between producers and consumers [7].

In Türkiye, consumer protection laws demonstrate features of both continuity and innovation. The role of pre-modern institutions like the guild organization and *Ahilik* has been crucial in guaranteeing market justice, maintaining standards of quality, and promoting ethical behavior. The contemporary legal system is relatively new compared to the aforementioned systems; indeed, the legal framework for protecting consumers was formally initiated with Article 172 of the Constitution of 1982. This article enshrined the duty of the State to provide consumer protection and information [5].

Consumer legislation in Türkiye was also affected in many ways by the process of economic liberalization and globalization. The passage of Law No. 4077 in 1995 marked the beginning of a serious attempt by the country to legislate for consumers' rights comprehensively [8]. This process took place in the context of global economic liberalization and the inclusion of Türkiye in the European economic system, especially the EU Customs Union, necessitating the alignment with the European Union's legal requirements. Another important reform included the adoption of Law No. 6502 in 2013 [10].

With the development of technology and the rise of e-commerce in recent times, there have been various problems that need to be tackled concerning consumer protection. Some of these include the problems of online payments, privacy concerns, misleading online advertisements, and international business issues, which require constant amendments in legislation. This has resulted in various amendments to consumer legislation in Türkiye.

In light of this background, the current research is intended to examine the history of the development of consumers' rights in Türkiye by tracing the evolution of these from their pre-modern beginnings to contemporary laws regulating this matter. Special attention will be paid to important stages of development such as constitutional provisions, legislative changes, and new regulations, and also put Türkiye's experience in this field in the larger context of global and European processes in order to understand the importance of consumer rights as an integral part of today's legal and economic environment.

Pre-Modern and Ottoman Influences

Consumer protection in Türkiye has an origin which dates back much before the modern system of law. There were provisions for fair dealing, trade, and safety from any form of deception and fraud right from ancient civilizations and socio-economic systems in the Ottoman Empire. It is evident through historical references that even in the ancient system of law, as well as religious principles such as the Code of Hammurabi and Roman law, there were provisions relating to fair dealing and safety from any form of fraud.

During the period of the Seljuks and Ottomans in the Turkish-Islamic world, the use of institutional methods to manage markets was quite prevalent. This included systems such as *Ahilik* and the use of guilds, which not only guaranteed quality and price fairness but also made sure that products were ethically produced and consumers were protected from any defects in goods or fraudulent activities [1]. The Ottoman *İhtisap* system was used to monitor markets, prevent fraud, and guarantee public welfare [13].

Consumer protection in Türkiye has deep historical roots extending from ancient legal traditions to the institutional structures of the Ottoman Empire. Long before the emergence of modern consumer law, various mechanisms were developed to regulate markets, ensure fairness in trade, and protect society against fraud and defective goods. Religious principles, customary rules, and state-supervised market systems collectively contributed to the formation of an early consumer protection culture. The

figure below illustrates the historical evolution of these practices and highlights the institutional and legal foundations that later influenced the modern Turkish consumer protection system (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Pre-Modern and Ottoman Influences on Consumer Protection in Türkiye
Source: Auhtor’s own.

The figure demonstrates the gradual evolution of consumer protection practices from ancient civilizations to the Ottoman legal-administrative structure. The first stage reflects the influence of early legal systems such as the Code of Hammurabi and Roman law, where principles of fairness, honesty, and protection against deception were already recognized. The second stage emphasizes the importance of Seljuk and Ottoman institutional mechanisms, particularly the Ahilik organization and guild system, which regulated production standards, ethical trade practices, and price fairness while protecting consumers from defective products and fraud. The third stage focuses on the Ottoman İhtisap system, which functioned as a market supervision mechanism aimed at preventing fraud, hoarding, and unfair commercial practices while maintaining public welfare and economic stability. Another important milestone presented in the figure is the Kanunnâme-i İhtisab-ı Bursa of 1502, regarded as one of the earliest systematic legal regulations concerning product quality standards, food safety, and fair business practices. This demonstrates that consumer protection in the Ottoman Empire was institutionalized through formal legal mechanisms. Finally, the figure illustrates that consumer protection during the Ottoman period was not primarily based on individual consumer rights, but rather on a broader moral economy shaped by religious principles, social responsibility, justice, and state supervision. These historical foundations significantly influenced the later development of modern consumer protection legislation in Türkiye.

During the period of the Seljuks and Ottomans in the Turkish-Islamic world, the use of institutional methods to manage markets was quite prevalent. This included systems such as *Ahilik* and the use of guilds, which not only guaranteed quality and price fairness but also made sure that products were ethically produced and consumers were protected from any defects in goods or fraudulent activities [1]. The Ottoman İhtisap system was used to monitor markets, prevent fraud, and guarantee public welfare [13].

An important turning point in history was the *Kanunnâme-i İhtisab-ı Bursa* (1502), which is seen as one of the first examples of systematic legislation related to product quality, food safety, and business practices [11]. These events show that consumer protection during the Ottoman period was

rooted in a larger system of moral economy and law enforcement, not personal rights.

Constitutional Foundations (1982 Constitution, Article 172)

The contemporary legal framework for consumer protection in Türkiye began after the enactment of the Constitution in 1982, especially Article 172, which says the State will endeavor to protect and educate consumers and foster their efforts in protecting themselves. This represented a paradigm shift because consumer protection became a constitutional responsibility.

The adoption of the 1982 Constitution marked a turning point in the development of consumer protection law in Türkiye. For the first time, consumer protection was recognized as a constitutional obligation of the State through Article 172. This constitutional provision transformed consumer protection from a moral and administrative concern into a legally guaranteed public responsibility. The constitutional framework also reflected Türkiye's transition toward a welfare-state model and coincided with the economic liberalization policies of the 1980s, which increased the need for stronger market regulation and consumer safeguards (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Constitutional Foundations of Consumer Protection in Türkiye: Article 172 of the 1982 Constitution and the Transition to the Welfare-State Model

Source: Author's own.

The figure illustrates the constitutionalization of consumer protection in Türkiye through Article 172 of the 1982 Constitution. It demonstrates the transition from traditional market regulation toward a welfare-state approach, emphasizing the State's responsibility to protect and educate consumers within the context of economic liberalization and expanding market relations during the 1980s.

The constitutionalization of consumer rights can be considered the result of shifting from the old model of regulating markets to the modern welfare-state model. Consumer rights are guaranteed by acknowledging the need for protection of consumers, who are vulnerable and exposed to bargaining power disparities and information gaps. Furthermore, it paved the way for future institutional and legislative measures [9].

Consumer protection in the Constitution was also connected with a process of economic liberalization in Türkiye in the 1980s. With the opening of the market economy, there arose the necessity to regulate its participants and protect consumers' interests.

The 1995 Consumer Protection Law (No. 4077) and EU Customs Union

An important landmark for Turkish consumer law came through the introduction of the Law No. 4077 for the Protection of Consumers in 1995. The law provided an overarching legal framework that addressed itself to the issue of protection of consumer rights in Türkiye for the very first time ever.

The enactment of Law No. 4077 on the Protection of Consumers in 1995 represented a major milestone in the modernization of Turkish consumer law. For the first time, Türkiye adopted a comprehensive legal framework specifically dedicated to the protection of consumer rights and the regulation of consumer–seller relations. The development of this legislation coincided with Türkiye’s integration into the European economic system through the EU–Türkiye Customs Union, which accelerated the harmonization of Turkish legislation with European Union standards in the field of consumer protection (See Figure 3).

Figure 3. The 1995 Consumer Protection Law (No. 4077) and EU Customs Union
Source: Author’s own.

The figure illustrates the significance of Law No. 4077 as the first comprehensive consumer protection legislation in Türkiye and demonstrates its connection with the EU–Türkiye Customs Union process. It highlights the key legal concepts introduced by the law, the harmonization reforms implemented through Law No. 4822 in 2003, and the broader alignment of Turkish consumer law with European Union standards and modern regulatory principles. Important concepts covered under the act include the notions of defective products, installment selling, consumer credits, unfair terms, and advertising.

The enactment of Law No. 4077 is related to the integration of the country in the economy of Europe, especially in the EU–Türkiye Customs Union in 1995. It required that Turkish laws be brought up to par with those in Europe, specifically on consumer protection, resulting in their modernization. Later revisions of the law, especially the passing of Law No. 4822 in 2003, further synchronized Turkish consumer law with EU regulations [3].

Therefore, Law No. 4077 must be viewed not only from a national context but also in relation to the process of bringing Turkish laws in line with EU norms.

The 2013 Reform: Law No. 6502 on Consumer Protection

One of the important changes was made due to Law No. 6502 on the Consumer Protection in 2013 that substituted Law No. 4077, and it introduced a new stage of evolution with more comprehensiveness, systematization, and harmonization with the *acquis* of the EU.

The adoption of Law No. 6502 on the Protection of Consumers in 2013 marked a new phase in the evolution of Turkish consumer law. Replacing Law No. 4077, the new legislation established a more comprehensive and systematic legal framework that significantly strengthened consumer rights and aligned Turkish law more closely with European Union consumer protection standards. The reform reflected the growing complexity of modern market relations, especially in areas such as electronic commerce, distance contracts, and financial services (See Figure 4).

Figure 4. The 2013 Reform: Law No. 6502 on Consumer Protection
 Source: Author's own.

The figure illustrates the major reforms introduced by Law No. 6502 and demonstrates how the legislation modernized the Turkish consumer protection system. It highlights the expansion of consumer rights into digital and financial transactions, the strengthening of remedies for defective goods and services, and the development of institutional mechanisms such as consumer arbitration boards and consumer courts. The figure also emphasizes the broader goals of consumer education, transparency, environmental awareness, and harmonization with European Union consumer protection standards.

In particular, Law No. 6502 extended the concept of consumer protection to include any consumer activity and transaction, for example, distance contracts, finance services, and online trade [4]. The law reinforced the rights of consumers concerning defective goods and services, providing opportunities for repairs, replacements, discounting, and cancellation of the contract.

More importantly, the legislation provided for the enhancement of institutional frameworks and dispute settlement mechanisms, including the importance of consumer arbitration boards and consumer courts. Additionally, it stressed consumer education, disclosure, and environmental concerns, indicating the multi-dimensional nature of consumer protection.

As noted in the literature, the 2013 Act is the apex of Türkiye's attempt at aligning its consumer protection framework with international and European trends.

Post-2013 Developments and Recent Updates

Since its passage in 2013, the Turkish consumer law has remained dynamic as it continues to

change in reaction to technology development, globalization trends, and the changing dynamics within the markets. The introduction and increased relevance of online platforms and e-commerce is among the most important changes that have happened.

Following the enactment of Law No. 6502 in 2013, Turkish consumer protection law has continued to evolve in response to technological innovation, globalization, and the rapid expansion of digital markets. The increasing importance of e-commerce, online platforms, and electronic transactions has required continuous legal adaptation in order to ensure effective consumer protection in the digital environment. Recent reforms demonstrate Türkiye's effort to modernize its legal framework and strengthen access to consumer rights and dispute resolution mechanisms (See Figure 5).

Figure 5. Post-2013 Developments and Recent Updates in Turkish Consumer Protection Law

Source: Author's own.

The figure illustrates the major developments in Turkish consumer protection law after 2013, particularly in the context of digitalization and market transformation. It highlights the rise of e-commerce and online platforms, enhanced legal protections for distance contracts, annual increases in monetary limits for consumer arbitration committees, the introduction of mandatory mediation in certain consumer disputes, and the growing role of online complaint platforms. The figure further demonstrates how these reforms have strengthened consumer rights, improved access to remedies, reduced the burden on courts, and aligned Turkish consumer protection practices with international and European standards.

The most recent updates to the Consumer Rights Act have revolved around distance contracts that give additional rights to consumers involved in online purchases. This is because of the increasing prevalence of internet business dealings.

Moreover, monetary limits for consumer arbitration tribunals are set every year; the limits for the year 2025 will raise the jurisdictions of these tribunals quite significantly. This makes it easier to resolve disputes and puts less pressure on the courts [2].

It is worth mentioning that mediation in some consumer disputes has become mandatory.

Moreover, the development of online consumer complaint sites has offered new ways to air

their grievances and get remedies, thus enhancing the participatory process in consumer protection.

Conclusion

History of consumer rights in Türkiye shows a continuous development of consumer rights protection from simple market regulation to a more advanced rights-based approach. Starting from primitive methods of regulation in ancient times to the modern era, there is evidence that consumer rights have been progressively protected and regulated by law.

The shift from Law No. 4077 to Law No. 6502, alongside various other reforms concerning digitalization and dispute resolution issues, is indicative of the willingness of Türkiye to bring its consumer legislation up to the international standard. Nowadays, Turkish consumer law can be regarded as a flexible and evolving sphere of law.

REFERENCES

1. Alkış A. İslam Hukukunda Tüketicinin Korunması // Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi. – 2019. – Vol. 16, No. 1. – P. 73–138.
2. Demir Ş., Seda B.A.Ş. Tüketici Hakem Heyetlerinde Parasal Sınır Uygulaması: Adalete Erişim ve Adil Yargılanma Hakları Bağlamında Bir Değerlendirme // Regesta Ticaret Hukuku Dergisi. – 2025. – Vol. 10, No. 3. – P. 1–40.
3. Eroğlu S.U. Tüketicinin Korunması Hakkında Kanun'un Kıymetli Evrak Hukukuna Etkileri // Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi. – 2004. – Vol. 6, No. 1. – P. 113–176.
4. Kazmacı Ö.U. İnternet ortamında kurulan mesafeli sözleşmelerde tüketicinin korunması // Marmara Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Hukuk Araştırmaları Dergisi. – 2016. – Vol. 22, No. 3. – P. 2791–2818.
5. Köycü H.K. Türkiye'de politika transferi etkisindeki bir kamu politikası alanı: Tüketicinin korunması // Turkish Studies – Economics, Finance, Politics. – 2021. – Vol. 16, No. 3.
6. Marsh P. The new industrial revolution: Consumers, globalization and the end of mass production. – New Haven: Yale University Press, 2012.
7. Morris M., Kaplinsky R., Kaplan D. “One thing leads to another” — Commodities, linkages and industrial development // Resources Policy. – 2012. – Vol. 37, No. 4. – P. 408–416.
8. Oruç M. 6502 Sayılı Tüketicinin Korunması Hakkında Kanun'un uygulama alanının eleştirisi // ICPESS 2017 Proceedings. – 2017. – Vol. 1.
9. Özalp L.F.A. İktisatta refah ve refah devletinin iktisadi analizi: Doktora tezi. – İstanbul: İstanbul Üniversitesi, 2016.
10. Özay O.L. 6502 Sayılı Yasa kapsamında tüketici işlemi // Avrasya Sosyal ve Ekonomi Araştırmaları Dergisi. – 2017. – Vol. 4, No. 12. – P. 257–272.
11. Özdemir R. Tüketici haklarına yönelik tarihte yapılan ilk kanun: “Kanunname-i İhtisab-ı Bursa” // Mecmua. – 2017. – No. 4. – P. 1–16.
12. Ruhl G. Consumer protection in choice of law // Cornell International Law Journal. – 2011. – Vol. 44. – P. 569–615.
13. Şahin H. Klâsik dönem Osmanlı ekonomisinde iktisadi kontrol araçları // Bartın Üniversitesi İİBF Dergisi. – 2014. – Vol. 5, No. 10. – P. 161–184.